

Impact of Gillnet of Three Mesh Sizes “2.5”, “3.5” and “4.5” on Sustainability of Fish Bio-diversity in Otamiri River, Imo State.

Onwuka C. N^{1*}., Ayegba E. O²., Ilesanmi A. I².

¹Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State.

²Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

*Corresponding author: onwuka.c@dou.edu.ng

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Abstract: The selectivity and catchability of three gillnets of mesh sizes “2.5”, “3.5” and “4.5” was used for fish sampling in Otamiri River between October 2022 and June 2023, a period of nine months, covering both dry and wet seasons. Sampling was done once a month along the river at demarcated points in the eighteen (18) sampling villages once in a month. The mesh size of “2.5” recorded highest fish catch of 2054 (60.94% of total fish catch). The gear of mesh size “3.5” recorded 921 catches (27.32%). The gear of “4.5” mesh size caught 395 (11.72%). The fish caught were mostly of species *Clarias/angillains*, *Anchenoglanis occidentalis*, *Anchenoglanis biscutatus*, *Melaterierus electrivus*, *Chromidotilapia guenterti*, *Hemichromis fasciatus*, *Tilapia dageti*. The occasional catches by the three types of gear mesh-sizes were *Gymnarchus niloticus*, *Tilapia zuli*, 5 and 3 for gear “2.5” and “3.5” and 4 and 12 for gear “4.5”. FisAT analysis revealed that the gear of “4.5” mesh size made for sustainable fishery in Otamiri River and is thus recommended for enforcement for use by all stakeholders.

Keywords: Fishing gear, Fish habitat, Fishing season, Water current.

Introduction

Fishing activities have been reported to be profitable amongst the fishers on the coast of Otamiri River, Orgi and Akabuche (1989); Ohaturuonye *et. al.* (2018). Meye (2013) showed that fishing activities in Nigerian streams, rivers and lakes are intense throughout the year. This is because the demand for fish has continuously out-weighted

supply (Meye and Ikomi, 2009). Solomon *et.al.* (2012) showed that the rapidly declining catch from fish landing is an indication that the fish yield of most Nigerian inland waters are generally low with reasons ranging from inadequate management of the fisheries and degrading of water ecosystem. Factors such as species being fished, individual value of the species to the fishers, depth of water and

fishing depth, characteristics of the seabed, the position of the gear to work in contact with the bottom, all these factors determine the choice of fishing gear to be used in a given area. The use of poor quality fishing materials can limit fish catch level, hence effort to maximize catch efficiency should be focused on improved fishing techniques and gears to enhance high productivity against low yielding traditional fishing methods (Tietze, 2005). Generally, fishing activities in water bodies are intense all year round, where fishers employ all types of fishing gears and sometimes obnoxious methods such as explosives to increase their catch (Idodo-Umeh, 2003). Olaniran (2003) stated that fishing gears have generally undergone a lot of modifications and improvement in consonance with advances in modern technology although the basic principle of wounding, hooking, trapping and encircling, scooping and filtering is being improved upon. Fish gears such as gill net, cast net, drift nets and seine nets are commonly used for fishing in most waters, probably due to the fact that these nets greatly influence catches, Olaniran (2003). Olaniran (2003) reported that the gears being used in the fishing activities in Eleyele Lake Ibadan are predominantly gill and cast nets. Gillnet is very popular amongst fishers in Nigeria and this account for about

75% of fisher-folks effort in Niger-Delta region (Francis and Sikoki, 2003). Knowledge of the efficiency of gillnet is important for estimation of fish population in stock assessment. The effects of technical innovation by fishers on the efficiency of gillnet is quantified in proper fisheries management. Netting material type has been shown to influence fish catches (Francis and Sikoki, 2003; Kingdom *et.al.*, 2015). Transparent monofilament netting material is effective in clear water (Olaniran, 2003). This is because the nets is invisible to the fish as visible nets tend to be avoided by fish. In turbid water however, the difference in structure and colour of gillnet material is usually very small. Gillnets are passive gears but can be used as active gears by dragging through water with the aid of two boats. The nets can be set passively on the surface, middle or bottom of the water. Kingdom *et al.* (2015) showed that the catchability of gillnet depends on its hanging on the water. The development of fishing technology in Nigeria is in line with the progress of fisheries science, including the knowledge of the gear efficiency and catchability in relation to fish handling. This knowledge is essential for efficient fishing and better fisheries resources management. Solarin and Kusemiji (2003) stated that transferring fishing effort from

individual fisheries to small-scale fisheries will have great benefits for the socio-economy of the fisheries sector as well as for the ecosystem in supporting the fisheries. However, in order for this to be realized, the level of information availability for small-scale fisheries should at least be as high as that of their industrial counterparts, with great need for improvement on knowledge of small-scale fisheries in Nigeria. The effectiveness of gillnets depends on factors which include mesh size, exposed net area, location, mesh shape, hanging ratio, visibility and type of netting materials in relation to stiffness and breaking strength, (Reis and Pawson, 1992). Gillnet is very popular among artisanal fishers in Nigeria. More than 25% of fishers in the inland coastal water in Nigeria uses gillnet at one time or another within a fishing season, (Otobotekere *et. al.*, 2009). Gillnets are passive gears but can be used as active gears by dragging through water with the aid of two boats. They can be set passively on the surface, middle or bottom of water, (Kingdom *at el.*, 2015).

Materials and Methods

Description of study area

The research was carried out at Otamiri River. Otamiri River originated at Egbu, in Owerri

North LGA and confluences with Nworie Stream in Owerri Municipal area. The River lies between the longitude 06°57' to 0.11°46' E and latitude 05°20' to 0.35°, 66°N' spanning 82 kilometers (Nwadiora and Okereke, 1993). The entire area lies within the Guinean Equatorial rain forest zone of Nigeria, 61-122m above sea level (Nwadiora and Okereke, 1993). The river starts as a first-order stream, then flows westward for about 7km to receive another first-order stream Nworie. From that point, it flows southwards as a second-order river for 28 kilometers and receives a major tributary, River Oramiruka. At the Oramiruka input, it continues southward for another 21km before it reaches Ogochia River, its third tributary in Etche LGA in Rivers State. It finally continues for another 26km downstream to the south near Owaza in Ikwerre LGA of Rivers State, where it discharges into Imo River. The length from source to mouth is approximately 82 kilometers. Otamiri River is not navigable due to its shallowness (mean depth 2.5m). It is highly transparent with numerous obstructions occurring along the main river channel. These include trees, logs, stumps, disused canoes and aquatic microphiles like Pistia, Azolia. The mean temperature is 26.7°C and range from 14.5 – 29.5°C, a clear indication that Otamiri is an acid water and characteristics of

forested river within the lower Niger Delta (Nwadiora and Okereke, 1993). The total suspended solids is 2.5mg l^{-1} while the mean dissolved oxygen concentration is 4.5mg l^{-1} (Nwadiora and Okereke, 1993). Otamiri River is under the influence of some perturbation due to human activities and inputs from the main feeder streams and sewage discharges from Owerri General Hospital, Alvanlko College of Education, Fuason Aluminum Company and Egebeada Federal Housing Estate. In addition, the ecology of river has greatly been altered by the activities of the indigenous local communities of Mgbirichi, Umuagwo and Umuapu villages who engage in dredging the river for commercial sand and gravel (Nwadiora and Okereke, 1993).

The Methodology in this research was adopted from Abowei and Hart (2008) using

Complete Sensors Technique. The entire length of the river was demarcated into three fishing zones to cover all the eighteen fishing communities of the river. Three fishers were hired to do the fishing using three specified gillnets of “2.5”, “3.5”, “4.5” mesh size. Fish composition was identified and evaluated using description checklist and keys and monographs in line with Olasebikan and Raji (1998). The fish samples were thereafter subjected to FiSAT Statistical Morphometric and Meristematic count. After fish sampling, the fish composition was compiled into an atlas of fisheries of Otamiri River as a reference material for literature and research purposes.

Figure 1 Map of study area showing the sampled stations

Fish Sampling Procedure

The sampling was done on the Eighteen (18) sampling villages as identified for this study along the coastal river course of Otamiri Rivers. However, the 18 identified villages were grouped into three sampling stations and mapped out as experimental sites to cover the 18 sampling villages. The sites are at:

- i. Onumiri Ezekwe (to cover the 5 indigenous coastal communities of Omumeri Mbeiri, Onumiri Akabar,

- ii. Onumiri Olokwu, Onumiri Richard Okoro Onumiri Ezeomee
- iii. Onumiri Nekede water side (to cover the coastal communities of Onumiri Mgbinchi/Ezekwe, Onumiri Umuoven, Onumiri Apostolic, Onumiri Oil-Mill, Onumiri Itioha.
- iii. Onumiri Ekwekere waterside (to cover the 5 indigenous coastal communities of Ohiagwa-Waterside, Eziebodo Waterside, Umuokpo Waterside, Umu-Usu

Waterside, Olokwu Waterside,
Ekwekere Waterside.

Fish sampling was done using three specified monofilament nylon gillnets with knob to knob mesh sizes of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80 and 100 mm. These nets each had a length of 10 meters and 2 meters hanging depth. On top, they were equipped with a cork line and underneath with a PVC lead line of 1.2kg/100m. Sets of these gillnets with the specified mesh sizes were dissembled in order of the mesh size to panels of 90 meters total length. The total surface area per panel was 180m² with 20m² of surface per mesh size. Hence this panel as described is the unit used to determine the catch per unit effort (CPUE) data. The sampling procedure involve certain three panels at the surface and to sink one at the bottom of the water.

In the process of identification of species, careful effort was to align observed morphology of the species to literature information, and data on geographical, spatial and temporal distribution as well as data on sex and feeding habits.

Efficacy of the three mesh size nets of “2.5”, “3.5” “4.5” was computed by merismetic count using FisAT computerized data system. This was achieved on the premise that the

mesh selective factor to determine the mesh opening of a gill-net is a variable that must take into account similar hanging ratios, to determine the shape of the netting panel as well as the shape of the individual meshes. In addition, the netting material and twine diameter used and the ballast and floatation specifications must also be considered. The method for estimating the Mesh Opening (Mo) required to gill a fish of length L in terms of the mesh selection favour Km is $Mo = L/km$. In order to utilize this formula, the fisher should have a set of known values based on prior sampling and/or fishing experience. If a gillnet with the mesh size M1 has caught fish of the length L1 and a gill net with the mesh size M2 catches fish of the length L2, then geometric similarity is expressed as: $L2/L1.2 = M2/M1$ which is also expressed as: $L2 \times L1 = M2 \times M1$. Therefore, the length of the fish L2 being the most frequent size of the fish caught with mesh size of M2 can be predicted by $L2 = L1 \times M2 \times M1$ conversely, the optimal mesh size M2 to be used for catching fish with a length ratio $L1 \times M1 = Km$ is specific for each species and/or anatomical shape of fish (Sistiaga *et al.* 2010). In this regard, all fish caught was identified and morphometric features well described.

Result

Composition Of Gillnet Catches

Table 1 Fish Species with Number % and Average Weight of Fish Species Caught with Gill-net of “2.5” Mesh Size

S/N	Fish Family	Species caught with gillnet of “2.5” mesh size	Total number of fish by species	% of total fish caught	Average Weight (g) of
1.	Notopteridae	Papyrocranus afer (Guther, 1869)	15	0.73	54
		Xenomystus nigri (Guther, 1868)	19	0.93	70
2.	Phractolaemidae	Phractolaemusans orgier (Boulenger, 1902)	30	1.46	90
3.	Hepsetidae	Hepsetus odoe (Bloch, 1794)	15	0.30	56
4.	Characidae	Brycinus longipinnis (Guther, 1864)	17	0.83	71
5.	Cyprinidae	Barbus callipterus (Boulenger, 1904)	31	1.54	69
6.	Polypteridae	Erpetoi chthyscalabaris (Smith, 1866)	18	0.88	52
7.	Pantodontidae	Pantodon buchhozii (Peter, 1877)	40	2.95	70
8.	Clariidae	Clarias gariepinus (Burchell, 1822)	19	0.93	52
		Clarias macromystax (Guther, 1864)	70	3.40	92
		Clarias angillaris (Linnaeus, 1758)	107	5.22	84
9.	Bagridae	Auchenoglanis occidentalis (Cuvier and Valenciennes, 1840)	140	2.95	102
		Auchenoglanis biscutatus (Geoffrey St. Hilaire, 1827)	120	5.84	97
		Epiplatyssex fasciatus (Gill, 1862)	25	1.22	58
10.	Cyprinodontidae	Epiplatyssex fasciatus (Gill, 1862)	25	1.22	58
11.	Malapteriuridae	Malapterurus electricus (Camelin, 1862)	107	5.01	80
12.	Nandidae	Polycentropsis abbreviata (Boulenger, 1901)	84	4.10	67
		Gymnarchus niloticus (Guvier, 1829)	5	0.24	32
14.	Cichlidae	Chromido-tilapia-guentheri (Sauvage, 1822)	209	10.17	102
		Hemichromis bimaculatus (Gill, 1862)	40	2.95	69
		Hemichromis fasciatus (Peters, 1862)	310	15.09	129
		Oreochromis niloticus (Linnaeva, 1758)	89	4.33	72
		Oreochromis aureus (Steindachner, 1864)	16	1.78	54
		Tilapia dageti (Thys Van de Audenaede, 1971)	150	7.30	102
		Tilapia zilli (Gervais, 1964)	3	0.15	25
15.	Clupeidae	Tilipia mariae (Boulenger, 1899)	58	3.82	62
		Ilisha africana (Bloch, 1795)	40	1.95	68
16.	Mormyridae	Brienomyrus bronchistius (Boulenger, 1879)	39	1.90	61
		Isicht hyshenryii (Gill, 1863)	72	3.51	95
		Hyperopisus-bebe-occidentalis (Guther, 1866)	79	3.85	103
		Parachanna africana (Steindachner, 1901)	15	0.73	51
17.	Channidae	Parachanna obscura (Guther, 1861)	55	2.68	29

18. Schilbeidae	Schilbeint ermeduis (Ruppel, 1832)	17	0.83	30
Total		2054	100	

Table 1 shows the species composition and the total catches on gillnet of mesh size “2.5”.

A total of 2054 species of 18 fish families were caught and identified. The most dominant fish caught were Cichlidae, Clariidae, Bagridae and Malapteriuridae families. The species caught included;

- (i) Cichlidae – Chromido-tilapia-quenther, (209), Hemichromis fasciation (310) Tilapia dageli (150 ms);
- (ii) Clariidae – Clarias angillaris (107 nos).

(iii) Bagridae – Auchendglariis occidentalis (140)

(iv) Auchemoglaris biscuralis (120)

(v) Malapteriuridae – Malapteruius electrius (107)

The best abundant of the species were of two main families.

(i) Gymnarchidae – Gymnarchus nilotius (5)

(ii) Cichlidae – Tilapia zilli (3)

These species formed occasional catch which do not really account for the main fishes of Otamiri river.

Table 2 Fish species with number % and Average weight of fish species caught with Gillnet of “3.5” mesh size.

S/N	Fish family	Species	Total number of fish caught with gillnet of “3.5” mesh size	% of total caught by Number	Average Weight (g) of total catch of each species
1.	Notopteridae	Papyrocranus afer (Guther, 1869)	8	0.86	65
		Xenomystus nigri (Guther, 1868)	9	0.97	70
2.	Phractolaemidae	Phractolaemusans orgier (Boulenger, 1902)	12	1.30	55
3.	Hepsetidae	Hepsetus odoe (Bloch, 1794)	7	0.76	35
4.	Characidae	Brycinus longipinnis (Guther, 1864)	9	0.97	62
5.	Cyprinidae	Barbus callipterus (Boulenger, 1904)	20	2.17	69
6.	Polypteridae	Erpetoichthys calabaris (Smith, 1866)	9	0.97	60
7.	Pantodontidae	Pantodon buchhozii (Peter, 1877)	19	2.06	61
8.	Clariidae	Clarias gariepinus (Burchell, 1822)	8	0.86	70
		Clarias macromystax (Guther, 1864)	14	1.52	60
		Clarias angillaris (Linnaeus, 1758)	38	4.22	81
9.	Bagridae	Auchenoglanis occidentalis (Cuvier and Valenciennes, 1840)	90	9.77	120
		Auchenoglanis biscutatus (Geoffrey St. Hilaire, 1827)	60	6.51	110
10.	Cyprinodontidae	Epiplatyssex fasciatus (Gill, 1862)	17	1.84	55
11.	Malapteriuridae	Malapteruius electrius (Camelin, 1862)	10	1.08	67

12.	Nandidae	Polycentropsis abbreviata (Boulenger, 1901)	55	5.99	90
13.	Gymnarchidae	Gymnarchus niloticus (Guvier, 1829)	70	7.60	120
14.	Cichlidae	Chromido-tilapia-guentheri (Sauvage, 1822)	3	0.32	60
		Hemichromis bimaculatus (Gill, 1862)	70	7.60	121
		Hemichromis fasciatus (Peters, 1862)	120	13.02	140
		Oreochromis niloticus (Linnaeva, 1758)	44	4.77	90
		Oreochromis aureus (Steindachner, 1864)	8	0.86	60
		Tilapia dageti (Thys Van de Audenaede, 1971)	70	7.60	90
		Tilapia zilli (Gervais, 1964)	2	0.23	58
15.	Clupeidae	Tilapia mariae (Boulenger, 1899)	20	2.17	71
		Ilisha africana (Bloch, 1795)	19	2.06	60
16.	Mormyridae	Brienomyrus bronchistius (Boulenger, 1879)	12	1.30	57
		Isichthys henryii (Gill, 1863)	31	3.36	80
		Hyperopisus-bebe occidentalis (Guther, 1866)	41	4.45	85
17.	Channidae	Parachanna africana (Steindachner, 1901)	7	0.76	37
		Parachanna obscura (Guther, 1861)	10	1.08	65
18.	Schilbeidae	Schilb eintermeduis (Ruppel, 1832)	9	0.97	68
	Total		921	100	

Table 2 shows the composition and the total catches on gillnet of mesh size. “3.5”. In total, 921 species in 18 families were caught using gill-net of mesh size “3.5”. The dominant fishes were Clariasangularis of Clariidae family, Auchenoglanis biscutatus of Brigridae

family, Polycentropsis abbreviate of Nandidae family, the Cichlidae were caught most in species as follows: Chromido tilapia guentheri (35), Hemichromis faciatus (41), Oreochromis niloticus (20), Clupeidae has Tilapia mariae (21) and Charidae (Parachanna africana (21)

Table 3 Fish Species with Number % and Average Weight of Fish Species Caught with Gill-net of “4.5” Mesh Size

S/N	Fish family	Species	Total number of fish caught with gillnet of “4.5” mesh size	% of total caught by Number	Average Weight (g) of total catch of each species
1.	Notopteridae	Papyrocranus afer (Guther, 1869)	6	1.52	70
		Xenomystus nigri (Guther, 1868)	5	1.30	54
2.	Phractolaemidae	Phractolaemusans orgier (Boulenger, 1902)	2	0.51	32
3.	Hepsetidae	Hepsetus odoe (Bloch, 1794)	6	1.52	56
4.	Characidae	Brycinus longipinnis (Guther, 1864)	7	1.77	69
5.	Cyprinidae	Barbuscal lipterus (Boulenger, 1904)	10	2.53	70
6.	Polypteridae	Erpetoichthys calabarisi (Smith, 1866)	3	0.76	49
7.	Pantodontidae	Pantodon buchhozi (Peter, 1877)	7	1.77	72
8.	Clariidae	Clarias gariepinus (Burchell, 1822)	8	2.03	39

		<i>Clarias macromystax</i> (Guther, 1864)	9	2.28	48
		<i>Clarias angillaris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21	5.32	70
9.	Bagridae	<i>Auchenoglanis occidentalis</i> (Cuvier and Valenciennes, 1840)	17	4.30	92
		<i>Auchenoglanis biscutatus</i> (Geoffrey St. Hilaire, 1827)	29	7.34	79
10.	Cyprinodontidae	<i>Epiplatyssex fasciatus</i> (Gill, 1862)	4	1.01	32
11.	Malapteruriidae	<i>Malapterurius electrius</i> (Camelin, 1862)	10	2.55	52
12.	Nandidae	<i>Polycentropsis abbreviata</i> (Boulenger, 1901)	21	5.32	78
13.	Gymnarchidae	<i>Gymnarchusni loticus</i> (Guvier, 1829)	4	1.01	40
14.	Cichlidae	<i>Chromido-tilapia guentheri</i> (Sauvage, 1822)	35	8.86	55
		<i>Hemichromis bimaculatus</i> (Gill, 1862)	8	2.03	42
		<i>Hemichromis fasciatus</i> (Peters, 1862)	41	10.08	35
		<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeva, 1758)	20	5.06	40
		<i>Oreochromis aureus</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	8	2.03	72
		<i>Tilapia dageti</i> (Thys Van de Audenaede, 1971)	21	5.32	48
		<i>Tilapia zilli</i> (Gervais, 1964)	12	3.04	35
15.	Clupeidae	<i>Tilipia mariae</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	4	1.01	40
		<i>Ilisha africana</i> (Bloch, 1795)	19	4.81	42
16.	Mormyridae	<i>Brienomyrus bronchistius</i> (Boulenger, 1879)	3	0.75	25
		<i>Isichthys henryii</i> (Gill, 1863)	21	5.32	40
		<i>Hyperopisus-bebe occidentalis</i> (Guther, 1866)	9	2.26	29
17.	Channidae	<i>Parachanna africana</i> (Steindachner, 1901)	3	0.74	15
		<i>Parachanna obscura</i> (Guther, 1861)	15	3.80	10
18.	Schilbeidae	<i>Schilb eintermeduis</i> (Ruppel, 1832)	7	1.77	17
	Total		395	100	

Table 3 shows the composition and the total catches on gillnet of mesh size. “4.5”. In total, 370 species in 18 families were caught using gill-net of mesh size “4.5”. The dominant fishes were *Clariasangularis* of Clariidae family, *Auchenoglanisbiscutatis* of Brigridae family, *Polycentropsis abbreviate* of Nandidae

family, the Cichlidae were caught most in species as follows. *Chromidotilapiaguentheri* (35 nos), *Hemichrainsfaciatus* (41 nos), *Oreochromisniloticus* (20 nos), Clupeidae has *Tilapia mariae* (21 nos) and Charidae (*Parachannaafricana* (21 nos)

Discussion

The experimental gillnet catches as presented in tables 1, 2 and 3 for mesh size “2.5”, “3.5” and “4.5” were dominated in terms of numbers both by families and species in fish Clarridae, Bagridae, Malapteriulla and Clupedae families. Most fish were caught in the gillnet of mesh size “2.5”, followed by gillnet “3.5”, the least catch of 370 was recorded with gear mesh “4.5”. The largest number of species were found in the family Bagridae and Cichlidae, found mostly in the flood plain areas. This may be done to the special characteristic of the habitat Meye (2013), who noted that African riverine fish fauna vary according to the type of bottom habitat and water current speed. In the Niger-Delta region where Otamiri, river is situated, Lowe-McConnell (1987) reported that where the bottom sand is fine and hard, it is frequented by the Characiids (Brycinuslongipinnis and the Cichlids (Tilapias) while in muddy bottom, Mormyrids and Catfishes (Clariids) predominate in muddy bottom.

Gillnet is a highly selective fishing gear and the oldest, widely use in fishing and harvesting species of fish (Andrew *et al.* 2007). According to Hovgard and Lassen (2000), the advantages of gillnet include low

cost, easy to use and set at any depth and in areas with difficult bottom conditions. Fish caught in gillnet are usually gilled but can be wedged, snagged or entangled (Hovgard and Lassen, 2000). Gillnets are considered as having a high degree of selectivity, in terms of fish species, as well as the size of the fish, which directly depends on the mesh size (Emmanuel *et al.*, 2008). Selectivity of fishing gear is the proportion of fish available to the gill in a given size or age group that is retained by the gear (Hunte and Mahon, 2001). The availability of the fish to the gear depends on the selective catchability of the gear, and fishing power and effort employed (Hovgard and Lassen, 2000) and the intensity of use of any form of gear is dependent on the intensity of fish population presumed to be available (Kurkilahti *et. al.* 2002). Gillnet selectivity studies can be carried out by fishing with gillnets of different mesh sizes to show changes on the catchability of fishes of different sizes (Kurkilahti *et. al.* 2002). Gillnet selectivity can be affected by factors such as gear parameters related to the fish, operation during fishing process, environmental parameters, pollution and turbidity of water (Holst *et al.*, 1998). Chindah and Tawari (2001) observed that larger size classes of fish were caught with increase in mesh sizes of nets. The hanging

ratio of gillnets is also one of the main determinants of the range of length of fish retained. Twine size and colour has been shown to affect the visibility of gill nets and therefore their effectiveness as a passive gear type (Kingdom *et al.*, 2015).

The result from the experimental gillnet fishing provides information on the composition of the gillnet catches, which provides information on productivity of the gear. Hence the selectivity of the gillnet is not only in terms of species but majorly in terms of size of the fish. In this study, it is seen that the gears of mesh size “2.5” and “3.5” caught more fish than that of mesh size “4.5”. The small mesh size will catch most fish whereas the larger mesh size will allow the small fish to escape. On gillnet fisheries, Emmanuel *et al.* (2008) reported a total number of 16 fish species belonging to 14 families and catch rates of pelagic fish in tropical coastal lagoonal ecosystem. Hickford *et al.* (1996) reported a total fish number of 3,284 of which is made up of 55 species on their study on catch characteristics of commercial gillnets in a near shore fishery in Central New Zealand.

This report is quite comparable with the result of this research, on the account of the indices of gear mesh size of “2.5”, “3.5” and “4.5” and the technical input employed. Therefore, the total number of species encounter in any given habitat is mainly higher than the number of species found in the same habitat at any given time. This is because there are shifts in the species composition throughout the season shifts that are closely linked to water quality in the habitats and the migration habitats of many species.

Conclusion / Recommendation

The use of gears of “2.5”, “3.5” and “4.5” mesh sizes in this research displayed the fish biodiversity of Otamiri river. Although the gear “2.5” and “3.5” mesh size caught more fish than “4.5” mesh size, the use of gear of “2.5” and “3.5” may not support sustainable fishing practices in Otamiri river. Therefore, Government, Fishery Professionals and all stakeholders are hereby encouraged to guard against the use of gears of smaller mesh sizes to support sustainable fishing in Nigeria waters.

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